

ISSUES OF FORMING THE THINKING OF YOUTH IN THE PROCESS OF
MODERNIZATION OF SOCIETY

Katayev Salaxiddin Valiql o'g'li

Teacher of Termez Institute of Agrotechnology and Innovative Development

Annotation. One of the most important factors during the period of modernization of society is the formation of the worldview, consciousness, and thinking of people. The article examines the participation and importance of youth in the process of modernization of society. The formation of the thinking of young people in this process is considered, especially during the transition from one period to the second, at turning points in history, in conditions when values are restored, updated, revalued.

Key words: modernization, mass culture, foreign culture, ideological attacks

One of the main directions of educating the younger generation in the modern period is to ensure that they have a high legal culture and maturity of legal knowledge. At this stage, we can consider higher education as a factor that actively influences various life processes in society, promotes the integration of youth and all social groups, ensures and strengthens the integrity and harmony of society. It is necessary to explain to young people that respect for the law is one of the main requirements for the effective functioning of a legal society, political and legal systems. Since legal culture is an integral part of the general culture, such confidence must be established in the minds of our youth that they consider human life, freedom, honor, dignity, rights and liberties to be sacred in a highly cultured and enlightened civil society.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, every person must be aware of their responsibility to the people, state, society and family. After all, there are many opportunities for rooting new democratic values on the disputed land of Uzbekistan, for creating a new modern political economy and social structures compatible with a secular legal democratic state and civil society, the idea of the priority of human rights and freedoms as the main wealth of human rights.

Unfortunately, today, first of all, ideological, ideological and information attacks remain very relevant, aimed at destroying the spiritual world of every person, regardless of language, religion, beliefs and the concept of spiritual threat. It is good that such ideological attacks attack our national and religious veins and have the evil goal of cutting us off from them. From this point of view, today education is an important

condition for the sustainable development of the country and the most important tool that helps us. Educators, that is, our youth, must have a moral basis.

Community spirituality is a product of social education. Therefore, the development of the scientific foundations of spiritual education is becoming one of the strategic directions for the spiritual renewal of society. Because it is difficult to preserve, restore and enhance the national identity and spirituality of our people without relying on the traditions of spiritual education. In addition, the following economic, social and cultural rights and norms should be respected:

- 1) the right to life is an inalienable right of every person;
 - 2) no one can arbitrarily deprive a person of life;
 - 3) no one should be subjected to suffering, cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment;
 - 4) no one should be forcibly detained;
 - 5) everyone has the right to freedom and privacy, no one can be arbitrarily arrested or detained;
 - 6) every person legally present in the territory of the state has the right to move freely and choose a place of residence within this territory;
 - 7) everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion.
- International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 19 December 1966 (Human Rights, 1997).

We know that the level of social consciousness of humanity develops and improves in accordance with time and place as a result of development. Accordingly, ideological threats manifest their essence and change from one form to another or give way to a new one. Such threats, i.e. ideas that cannot be predicted at first glance, what features they have, whether they can cause positive or negative consequences, "globalization processes," threats under the guise of "popular culture" and "export of democracy," "information attack," and based on it one can include the widely developing "virtual jihad" and "cyberterrorism", new forms of religious extremism and fundamentalism. The fact that such "hybrid ideas" know no boundaries, do not choose time and place, requires constant vigilance in this regard in our country. In particular, the process of globalization has a complex impact on all spheres of society, including the spiritual sphere, on modern youth, and this situation can cause situations in which our youth, students, believe and later follow it.

Today, many young people dream of the West and strive to live a Western life. He will stop at nothing to achieve his goal. He does not believe in the development of his country. This situation occurs mainly under the influence of mass culture. Products

of "popular culture" are called "kitsch" products. Kitsch in German means "cheapening". So, kitsch is not an original thing, but a copy of it, a cheap imitation of an expensive thing. This means creating something artificial. This also applies to morality. That is, not being kind, pretending to be kind, not being a real friend, pretending to be a friend, etc. The more independent-minded people with demanding tastes in society, the larger the market for mass culture will be, since they place high demands on the products they eat, drink, wear, hear, see and read. It is necessary to prevent ideological and political forces from spreading false information about our country or society among students of higher educational institutions. Otherwise, young people's trust in their society and development path will weaken. Today, various evil forces in the world are trying to make maximum use of all methods and means of evil for their own purposes. Such forces now continue to destroy the spirituality of people, poison the minds of young people, lose national values that have developed over centuries, and weaken their faith and national feelings. Our youth must understand that the processes taking place in society under modernization were based on objective laws, the violation of which can lead to serious consequences. We must always remember that the above is an important concept that shows cultural progress, that society has traveled a long and difficult path until it has reached today's progress, and that this path helps it differentiate between what is good and what is bad, white and black.

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